

A Case Study of Intrapreneurship Initiatives in Moroccan Family Businesses

Une étude de cas des initiatives d'intrapreneuriat dans les entreprises familiales marocaines

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Abstract

This study explores the role of organizational aspects of intrapreneurship in family businesses in Morocco, focusing on corporate culture, business policies and practices, and organizational structures. The results highlight their importance in fostering intrapreneurship. Through a case study involving five participants, conducted within a family business characterized by a propensity for innovation and strong support for entrepreneurship, the importance of a corporate culture that encourages creativity and risk-taking, policies and practices that foster intrapreneurship, and organizational structures that facilitate collaboration and communication, is highlighted. These results indicate significant implications for Moroccan family businesses wishing to promote intrapreneurship, highlighting the need to put in place policies and practices supporting innovation and fostering a corporate culture valuing creativity and risk-taking.

Keywords: Intrapreneurship; Family businesses; Corporate culture; Corporate policies and practices; Organizational structures

Résumé

Cette étude explore le rôle des aspects organisationnels dans l'intrapreneuriat des entreprises familiales au Maroc, en se concentrant sur la culture d'entreprise, les politiques et pratiques d'entreprise, ainsi que les structures organisationnelles. Les résultats soulignent leur importance pour favoriser l'intrapreneuriat. À travers une étude de cas impliquant cinq participants, menée au sein d'une entreprise familiale caractérisée par une propension à l'innovation et un fort soutien à l'entrepreneuriat, l'importance d'une culture d'entreprise encourageant la créativité et la prise de risque, de politiques et pratiques favorisant l'intrapreneuriat, ainsi que de structures organisationnelles facilitant la collaboration et la communication, est mise en évidence. Ces résultats indiquent des implications significatives pour les entreprises familiales marocaines souhaitant promouvoir l'intrapreneuriat, en soulignant la nécessité de mettre en place des politiques et pratiques soutenant l'innovation et en favorisant une culture d'entreprise valorisant la créativité et la prise de risque.

Mots clés : Intrapreneuriat ; Entreprises familiales ; Culture d'entreprise ; Politiques et pratiques d'entreprise ; Structures organisationnelles

Introduction

- In a turbulent environment where nothing is certain or guaranteed, companies are faced with a series of challenges that affect all the decisions they have made in the past, and the need for innovation increases as companies make a permanent commitment to sustainability. "There is nothing more difficult to take in hand, more perilous to direct, or more uncertain, than to engage in the establishment of a new order of things, for innovation has for enemies all those who have prospered under past conditions and has for lukewarm defenders all those who can prosper in the new order." Niccolò Machiavelli Innovation is obviously a source of creation, through the change in techniques, products and even human relations that it brings. Innovation is therefore seen as a vector of economic progress, by broadening outlets, creating jobs and qualifications, enabling new organisational practices, increasing productivity, and transforming usage patterns and mentalities is a central concept of competitive advantage.

Competitive advantage is necessarily the result of a process of innovation. Competitive advantage is based on a different way of performing a series of activities that deliver a unique set of values. But innovation is also destructive. Schumpeter, in a pithy phrase, wrote that innovation is "creative destruction", a paradoxical formula that explicitly expresses the two sides of the phenomenon. Taking family businesses as an example, innovation renders certain skills obsolete, eliminates jobs and dissolves the established order.

For decades, family businesses in most parts of the world have regularly acted in an entrepreneurial manner, demonstrating persistent behaviour based mainly on the pursuit of initiatives (Stevenson and Jarillo, 1990), risk-taking, proactivity, capacity for innovation, autonomy and competitive aggressiveness (Lumpkin and Dess, 1996). In addition, many families involved in business demonstrate an entrepreneurial spirit that is passed down from generation to generation and spreads very widely within the family, which then acts as an incubator for entrepreneurial culture (Steier, 2009).

This state of mind, which encourages and facilitates initiative and innovative behaviour on the part of family members, results in the creation and takeover of businesses. This question of encouraging entrepreneurship through the family is often raised, especially when it comes to family businesses, since one of the main characteristics of family businesses, often highlighted in the literature, is the quest for longevity.

Furthermore, a number of studies have shown that these firms draw from their family dimension the ability to build certain competitive advantages, including the capacity for innovation that they develop through entrepreneurship. In this respect, what is known as intrapreneurship or organisational entrepreneurship enables all companies to create and maintain an entrepreneurial culture within the existing business. In turn, this spurs innovation in support of diversification strategies, expansion plans and the penetration of new markets. Furthermore, intrapreneurs become great business leaders because they develop general leadership skills, are comfortable working in an unfamiliar environment, learn to make decisions with little information, are not afraid to challenge the status quo and are often able to spot initiatives where others see none. It is important to look at some of these preconceptions and define how intrapreneurship should be deployed in the context of the family business.

Once created, a business evolves, changes and renews itself. These elements support the main idea that, in order to succeed, intrapreneurship must be implemented within the framework of strategic management. The literature on intrapreneurship in Moroccan family firms has mainly focused on the individual aspects of intrapreneurship, such as the personality, skills and motivations of intrapreneurs. However, the role of organisational aspects in intrapreneurship remains little studied. This research aims to answer a key question:

How can Moroccan family businesses create an environment conducive to intrapreneurship?

With this in mind, we will focus on the role of organizational aspects in promoting intrapreneurship within these companies. Specifically, we will explore the impact of corporate culture, corporate policies and practices, and organizational structures on the propensity for intrapreneurship. Before going into the details of the content, it is important to provide a brief overview of the methodology adopted in this study. To this end, we conducted an in-depth case study within a family-owned company representative of the Moroccan context. This case study involved five key interviewees, selected for their expertise and involvement in intrapreneurship processes within their company. Data were collected through semi-structured interviews and in-depth analysis of internal company documents.

This research is important because it will provide a better understanding of how Moroccan family businesses can create an environment conducive to intrapreneurship. In this study, we will focus on the role of organisational aspects in intrapreneurship in Moroccan family firms.

We will examine how corporate culture, company policies and practices, and organisational structures can influence intrapreneurship.

1. Family intrapreneurship

1.1. The growth of intrapreneurship

-Intrapreneurship is a real phenomenon that is spreading to the heart of companies, enabling them to accelerate their growth and modernise their organisational model. accelerate their growth and modernise their organisational model. There are several definitions of intrapreneurship, all of which have the process of innovation in common. Intrapreneurship was born in 1976 in the United States, a concept created by Pinchot, 1985 and Koenig, 1990. Intrapreneurship is defined as "a process that occurs within existing company, whatever its size, and which leads not only to new businesses, but also to other businesses, but also to other innovative activities and directions, such as the new products, services, technologies, administrative techniques, strategies and competitive postures" According to Teglberg, & al. 2010 innovation through employee contribution of employees can bring competitive advantages to the company. There are many definitions of intrapreneurship, but there is no consensus. According to (Carrier, 1996) the terms intrapreneurship and corporate entrepreneurship describe an entrepreneurial situation entrepreneurial situation within a very large company. Other terms are used, such corporate venturing, intrapreneurship and internal corporate entrepreneurship. The wide range of definitions leads to a a multitude of situations and contexts of intrapreneurship within companies and makes it possible to establish common points. The process of creating activities, products and/or services, as well as the process of acquiring resources and learning through the emergence of new situations and practices. Nevertheless, some researchers have favour narrower definitions, excluding small businesses and focusing on very large ones. Intrapreneurship is a cross-border activity that affects all areas of business. Its use requires the consideration and mastery of two essential levers such as its function and role, and the psychological characteristics necessary for its application (see figure 2). When we talk about psychological characteristics at this level, we are talking about the level of of preparation of the intrapreneur and also of the company, so we see that this activity is not just an entrepreneurial affair, but a clear risk-taking exercise.

Category 1: the different aspects of intrapreneurship

Source: Champagne & Carrier (2004)

- The diagram above shows the need for, and effects of, intrapreneurship on all areas of the company. areas of the business, such as corporate strategy, i.e., the company's programme for achieving its objectives, and the innovation process, through which we can determine whether the company is in a position to launch an innovative project and assess its capacity to innovate. Intrapreneurship can only be implemented in organisations that adopt an open approach and place a high priority on innovation. that are open to innovation and creativity, Otherwise, it requires a global organisational change that can lead to an organisational structure, such as models, processes and practices.

1.2. Intrapreneurship in family business

-Family businesses are key players in national and international economic growth and development. They play a very important role in creating new jobs and generating innovation if they engage in entrepreneurial activities. There is a strong contribution from organisational culture, generational involvement entrepreneurial characteristics of these family businesses on the implementation of the intrapreneurial idea.

1.2.1. Organisational culture in family businesses

Organisational culture refers to the consistent pattern of beliefs and values that represent acceptable solutions to key organisational issues. According to RBV, organisational culture can be a strategic resource that generates sustainable competitive advantage by encouraging learning, risk-taking and innovation. Family businesses are also difficult for competitors to

imitate, by virtue of their ambiguous origins and their roots in family history and dynamics. Organisational culture is an interdependent system made up of artefacts, adopted values and underlying assumptions. The interconnected nature of the tangible and intangible assets of family businesses also prevents the imitation of their cultures. As we have seen, owners and managers are often one and the same, which alleviates the problem of aligning principal and agent objectives. This alleviates concerns about opportunistic agent behaviour, reduces the need for contractual controls and monitoring and increases the use of social controls such as trust. Reduced reliance on controls and co-ordination increases the importance of a company's culture as a key determinant of its behaviour and therefore increases the possibility of intrapreneurial ideas being implemented.

1.2.2. Entrepreneurial characteristics of family businesses

Family businesses are companies that are family-owned and where more than half of the management team is made up of family members. The entrepreneurial functions of family members are composed of six dimensions: locus of control, need for achievement, propensity to take risks, tolerance of ambiguity, self-confidence and capacity for innovation. The implementation of the intrapreneurial idea is envisaged as a multidimensional structure that covers the dimensions "innovation", "risk-taking" and "proactivity". Intrapreneurship includes a variety of activities, such as developing new products and services and services, risk-taking and proactivity to enable organisational innovation and sustainability. and organisational sustainability. Nevertheless, making investment decisions about intrapreneurship is not as simple as defining it.

The values and perspective of family members in family businesses determine the family business's attitude towards attitude towards intrapreneurship activities. Therefore, depending on the entrepreneurial characteristics of family members, while in some family businesses family businesses, intrapreneurial activities are more intense and innovative investments are encouraged, in other family businesses, priority is given to protecting the status quo or protection of the status quo or opportunities in the environment cannot be apprehended.

In family businesses, the founding generation tends to maintain the status quo, while the tendency of later generations to do business with new means and methods outweigh those of previous generations. Doing business with new means and methods.

As a result, although the first generations family businesses need a special technical infrastructure and an entrepreneurial entrepreneurial personality to be able to start a new

business, subsequent generations should in this respect, differences in the degree of intrapreneurship can be observed between family members of different generations. family members of different generations. For this reason, intrapreneurship is very important for family businesses managed by future generations, as it enables them to ensure the continuity of their business and create employment opportunities.

2. Family intrapreneurship through the prism of the kuratko model

Regarding Intrapreneurship, in 1970, Collins and Moore were the first researchers who noted the distinction between Entrepreneurship and Intrapreneurship They stated that Entrepreneurs establish new organizations independently while Intrapreneurs create new structures inside an organization (Collins and Moore, 1970).

In 1973, Susbauer invented the word “Intrapreneurship” to describe entrepreneurship inside organizations, which includes establishment of relatively independent units inside the organization which allow the members of the organization to work with the same high morale, freedom of acting, and commitment (Susbauer, 1973). In 1985, Pinchot invented the word “Intrapreneurship” by merging the words “Intra” and “Entrepreneurship” and defined an Intrapreneur as a person who performs the tasks of an entrepreneur inside big organizations, including creating new units in the organization, presenting products, and inventing new processes which lead companies to development and profitability (Pinchot, 1985).

To be successful, Intrapreneurship has to be carried out through strategic management. Intrapreneurship has to be a complementary part of an organization’s wide strategic plans (Kuratko and Hodgetts, 2002). For this purpose, researchers have presented several models in which all essential activities and effective factors of the process are considered. These include:

- Cornwall and Perlman’s Intrapreneurship model (Kuratko and Hodgetts, 2002) which is based on a strategic management approach. Information gathered from the outside and the inside environment of the organization marks the initiation of the Intrapreneurship process. This information is necessary to evaluate strategic choices and to choose the best strategic plan which is administered afterwards.
- Echols and Neck’s Intrapreneurship model (Kuratko and Hodgetts, 2002) which tries to conceptually examine effects of individuals’ entrepreneurial behaviors and entrepreneurial organizational structure on the success of the entrepreneurship. In

other words, this model shows an organization's ability to exist in a dynamic environment that is overwhelmed by innovation.

- Thompson's entrepreneurship dimensions (Kuratko and Hodgetts, 2002). For implementing entrepreneurship in organizations, Thompson considers five dimensions: hard entrepreneurship, soft entrepreneurship, risk-taking, idea and plan presentation, and innovation. Existence of all these dimensions is indispensable for entrepreneurial organization.

-Kuratko's Intrapreneurship model. In this model, the creation process of new entrepreneurial business is the product of interaction between several factors. Also, a decision to initiate entrepreneurship in an organization is a result of interaction between organizational attributes, individuals' characteristics, and some catalysts (Kuratko and Hodgetts, 2002). Kuratko believes that the concept of Intrapreneurship is similar to that of entrepreneurship except that the former occurs in an organization which already exists. Consequently, by building an entrepreneurial spirit inside the organization's borders, the atmosphere is changed remarkably.

In our paper, we aim to present the different advantages of intrapreneurship using the model of Kuratko and Hodgetts, 2002. We have come to the conclusion that Kuratko's model corresponds better to the conditions of the family business chosen as a case, since it is a highly strategic organisation and the environment seems dynamic. In this model, the process of creating a new business is the product of the interaction between several factors.

Similarly, the decision to create a business within an organisation is the result of an interaction between the attributes of the organisation, the characteristics of individuals and certain catalysts (Kuratko and Hodgetts, 2002).

In addition, we will use the theoretical framework of Jong and Wennekers (2008), based on Kuratko's (2002) model, to explore intrapreneurship initiatives through organisational characteristics.

Category 2: factors influencing intrapreneurial behaviour

- Organisational culture in family businesses
- Entrepreneurial characteristics in family businesses

Source: Jong and Wennekers, (2008)

3. Methodology

In our article, the choice of a single case study is based on several methodological and theoretical considerations, in line with the principles put forward by researchers such as Yin (1994) and Gagnon (2012).

According to Yin (1994), the use of a single case study is justified in specific situations where the case is critical for testing an existing theory, represents an extreme or unique case, or allows an established theory to be challenged. This approach is also advocated by Gagnon (2012) for crude empirical problems, phenomena little explored in the academic literature. In the context of our research on intrapreneurship initiatives within a Moroccan family business, the choice of a single case study is motivated by several factors. Firstly, this study allows us to explore in depth a specific case that offers unique or extreme characteristics relevant to our object of study. By choosing a family business characterised by a strong propensity for innovation and support for entrepreneurship, we can examine intrapreneurial dynamics in detail in a specific and complex context.

3.1. Sample

For this study, a sample of five key managers from the selected family business was selected. The selection criteria were defined to include members of the owning family or individuals with significant involvement in the operational and strategic management of the business.

These participants were chosen for their expertise and direct experience of organisational practices and intrapreneurial dynamics within the family business, thus ensuring an in-depth perspective on the subject under study.

SITI TEA is a Moroccan company specialising in the packaging of luxury teas and infusions. Founded in 1979, it is now a world leader in its field.

The company is the flagship of Imperium Holding, a Moroccan agri-food group. It exports its products all over the world and works with major international brands. SITI TEA offers a wide range of packaging solutions, including top-of-the-range tea bags, metal tins and loose tea packaging. It is recognised for its expertise in high-end packaging.

SITI TEA's projects include

- The design and production of high-end packaging for a British tea brand.
- The development of a new range of organic tea bags for a French brand.
- The creation of eco-responsible packaging for an American brand.

SITI TEA is an innovative company that has positioned itself as a key player in the luxury tea and infusions market. generations, based on their company's entrepreneurial spirit and performance.

On the other hand, in family-run businesses that are managed together by family members from different generations, the estimates and identification of opportunities effectively provide a diversity of knowledge that will enable opportunities to be opportunities into innovations and entrepreneurial activities. This is why the continuity of family businesses to protect family assets and job creation across generations.

It depends primarily on the entrepreneurial efforts on the entrepreneurial efforts of the next generation, because the generations to come are effective drivers of performance,

innovation and entrepreneurial Kuratko believes that the concept of intrapreneurship is similar to that of entrepreneurship, except that the former is similar to a process of creating a business in an organisation that already exists. Consequently, by developing entrepreneurship within the boundaries of the organisation, the atmosphere is remarkably altered.

3.2. Data collection

Data was collected through in-depth semi-structured interviews with the five selected managers. These interviews were conducted individually to allow for an open and detailed discussion of intrapreneurship initiatives within the family business. A structured interview guide was drawn up in advance, based on the objectives of the study and the research areas identified. This guide included open-ended questions designed to explore key aspects such as organisational culture, resource management and the challenges encountered in promoting intrapreneurship within family businesses. The interviews were recorded with the consent of the participants and then transcribed in full to form the basis of subsequent data analysis.

3.3. Data analysis

To explore initiatives for intrapreneurship, we had to look at the company from different angles. The first step was to obtain 'general recognition' of the organisation. The best way to achieve this is probably to gather and clarify the views of managers (family members) and assistant managers about their company. To this end, a semistructured interview guide was designed with the aim of examining the effective factors for intrapreneurship and we conducted the interviews physically within the company. The results were then obtained through a content analysis. Having acquired this general knowledge, the next step was to find idea generators and creative employees within the company. After several examinations, it was concluded that an intrapreneurial project is led by a family member and his team, who manage two aspects.

Based on the observation that "One of the signs of intrapreneurship in an organisation is the implementation of new ideas". One of the most important initiatives observed is "kilou.ma", which was an idea proposed by one of the family members and implemented by one of the IT specialists and managed by a team of intrapreneurs who contributed to the success of this idea. To find out about the initiatives and factors involved in implementing an approved idea in an organisation, we conducted interviews with managers.

Finally, the views of managers, assistant managers and specialists were collected, studied and evaluated using Kuratko's model. Initiatives for intrapreneurship were then extracted according to the factors in this model. These initiatives are as follows.

The data from the interviews was analysed using a thematic analysis approach. This method involved several steps: firstly, the transcripts were read and coded to identify recurring themes and motives relating to intrapreneurship. Next, the codes were grouped into broader thematic

categories to structure the results in a coherent way. Finally, the themes identified were interpreted in the light of the theoretical framework and objectives of the study, allowing significant conclusions to be drawn about the practices and challenges of intrapreneurship in the family business studied. This rigorous analysis highlighted the specific organisational dynamics that promote or hinder intrapreneurship initiatives in the family context, providing valuable insights for research and practice in this area.

4. Initiatives for intrapreneurship in the family business studied:

Gathering and classifying information according to Kuratko's model enabled us to find the origin of these initiatives in the organisation observed.

4.1. Availability of resources (Bernhard, 1996)

4.1.1. Emotional support

The interviewees' statements reveal a deep understanding of the essential role of emotional support within the family in the professional context. The notion of perception, emphasised in the first sentence, underlines the subjectivity of this experience.

The interviewees highlight the fact that emotional support is not limited to a simple objective reality, but also depends on how a family member perceives it. This nuance underlines the importance of emotional ties and individual feelings in the family fabric, particularly in a professional context. The intrapreneur, as a specific member of the family mentioned, embodies the way in which this emotional support comes to life in everyday reality.

The fact that this support was expressed by his brothers when the idea was proposed by his team adds a collaborative and intergenerational dimension to the story. The concrete actions mentioned illustrate the brothers' active involvement in the intrapreneur's success, underlining a profound family unity.

The interviewees also underline the notion of team, pointing out that emotional support is not limited to the extended family, but also extends to colleagues and the professional team. This collective dimension of support reinforces the idea that professional success is not the result of isolated individual efforts, but rather of harmonious collaboration between family members and colleagues.

The concrete actions mentioned by the interviewees are a particularly notable aspect of their statements. These concrete gestures are not limited to words of support, but include tangible actions, testifying to active involvement and genuine family solidarity. This tangible demonstration of emotional support can take various forms, such as active participation in

professional discussions, contribution of ideas, or even direct investment in the intrapreneur's project.

The importance of communication within the family also emerges from these statements. The brothers took the time to understand the proposed idea, underlining the importance of open communication and listening to each other. This constructive communication helps to create an environment where innovative ideas can flourish, reinforcing the feeling of emotional support.

The interviewees' statements also highlight the continuity of emotional support throughout the process, from the initial proposal to the actual implementation of the project.

This underlines the fact that emotional support is not ephemeral, but rather a constant pillar, offering stability and assurance to the intrapreneur throughout their career. The emotional and relational implications of this family dynamic are also reflected in the statements made by the interviewees.

The intrapreneur's professional success is perceived as a collective success, strengthening family ties and creating a shared sense of pride. This emotional dimension underlines the fact that family support is not limited to purely professional considerations, but has profound ramifications for the emotional well-being of each individual.

4.1.2. Informational support

The interviewees' statements significantly underline the importance of informational support within the family in the professional context of intrapreneurship. The very definition of informational support, centred on the perception of being supported by the provision of information or advice, highlights the value of shared knowledge within the family. The fact that family members introduced the intrapreneur to a range of business clients before the intrapreneurial idea was put in place is a crucial step in the development process. This action demonstrates a particular proactivity and commitment on the part of the family to the professional success of the intrapreneur.

By sharing strategic information about potential customers and promoting the use of the Kilou.ma platform, the family has provided the intrapreneur with a wealth of valuable information. The collaborative aspect of this approach is clear from the statements made by the interviewees. The fact that family members mobilised to identify and present business initiatives suggests close collaboration and a collective effort in favour of the intrapreneurial

project. This goes beyond mere informational assistance to become a tangible demonstration of the family's active involvement in the intrapreneur's success.

The statements also highlight the strategic timing of this provision of information. By providing this data before the intrapreneurial idea is put in place, the family has not only demonstrated wise foresight, but has also enabled the intrapreneur to make informed decisions early in the process.

This anticipation and advance preparation can be seen as a form of preventive support, aimed at minimising potential risks and maximising the chances of success.

The reference to the use of the Kilou.ma platform adds a technological dimension to the equation. This suggests that the family not only provides information in a general way, but also directs the intrapreneur to specific tools and technological resources that can enhance the implementation of their idea. This underlines the relevance of informational support, taking into account technological trends and innovative solutions.

The interviewees' statements highlight the proactive nature of informational support, emphasising that the family does not simply react to the intrapreneur's needs, but actively anticipates those needs. This level of early involvement creates an environment conducive to innovation, where the family acts as a catalyst for the intrapreneur's professional progress.

4.1.3. Instrumental support

The interviewees' responses highlight the crucial importance of instrumental support within the family, particularly in the professional context of intrapreneurship. The very definition of instrumental support, centred on the perception of being supported by concrete actions, underlines the value of practical gestures and tangible assistance provided by family members. The intrapreneur, by stating that Kilou had a stockpile within the company and that it was managed by all teams without discrimination, underlines a practical and inclusive dimension of instrumental support.

The provision of stock within the company represents material assistance, a tangible resource made available in an accessible way. The management of this stock by all teams, without discrimination, demonstrates an equitable and collaborative approach, reinforcing the instrumental nature of family support. The practical nature of this assistance extends beyond the simple provision of material resources. It shows an active willingness on the part of the family to get involved in the operational and logistical aspects of intrapreneurship. The involvement of all teams, without distinction, underlines a culture of equality and

collaboration within the family business, creating an environment conducive to the intrapreneur's success.

The responses also highlight the inclusive nature of the instrumental support. The fact that stock is managed by all teams, without discrimination, demonstrates a holistic approach that recognises the value of the contribution of every member of the business.

This not only contributes to the success of the intrapreneur, but also strengthens the sense of belonging and commitment of all family members involved in the project. The positive impact of this instrumental support goes beyond simply helping with administrative tasks. By providing an inclusively managed stock, the family acts as a key facilitator of the intrapreneur's operational efficiency.

This practical assistance can free up time and resources, allowing the intrapreneur to focus more on the strategic aspects of their project, thereby enhancing their potential for success. The intrapreneur's statement also suggests collaborative resource management, highlighting that stock was managed by all teams. This goes beyond simple administrative assistance to become a demonstration of the family's collective commitment to the operational management of the business. This cross-functional collaboration strengthens cohesion within the team, creating an environment conducive to innovation and professional synergy.

4.2. Organisational support (Siebels, 2002)

4.2.1. Autonomy

The interviewees' responses highlight a significant aspect of the family context in relation to autonomy in the workplace. The definition of autonomy, presented as a measure of the freedom a family member has to make their own decisions, highlights a particular nuance in family dynamics in relation to work responsibilities. The interviewees expressed that autonomy was not strongly present in their statements, stressing that any decision had to be accepted by both the team and the family members, as it represents the family as a whole. This observation reveals a delicate balance between the freedom to make individual decisions and the need to take into account the impact of these decisions on family cohesion and identity.

The fact that decisions must be accepted by both the team and the family members indicates a consultative and collective approach to the decision-making process. This underlines the priority given to family cohesion and unity rather than total individual autonomy. The family is perceived as an entity whose values and decisions must be shared, which may limit

individual autonomy in favour of family harmony. However, this observation does not completely deny the possibility of autonomy.

The simple fact that the decision has to be accepted by the team and family members suggests a space for discussion and persuasion. This implies that although individual autonomy may be conditional, there are initiatives for family members to advocate for their decisions, reinforcing the notion of collaborative decision-making.

The focus on family representation in each decision reflects the value attached to family identity. Interviewees emphasised that each decision represents the family, underlining the collective dimension of professional responsibility.

This perspective highlights the way in which individual autonomy is subordinated to the preservation of family image and values, thus underlining the complexity of the relationship between the professional and personal life. This collective approach can also be interpreted as a form of mutual protection within the family. By limiting individual autonomy, the family may be seeking to avoid potential conflict and ensure that decisions taken are aligned with shared goals and values. It may also help to strengthen family solidarity by ensuring that all decisions are taken in the common interest.

4.2.2. Flexibility

The interviewees' statements highlight the dimension of flexibility in family work, particularly with regard to the control of time. The importance attached to temporal flexibility emerges as a central element in the organisation of family work, while also highlighting certain limits inherent in the obligations linked to tasks outside Kilou.ma. The statement notes that flexibility in terms of time is widely present, suggesting an approach that values freedom in the management of work schedules. This flexibility can be interpreted as a recognition of the diversity of family and work responsibilities, offering family members the opportunity to tailor their schedules to meet their individual needs. However, the statement adds an important nuance by emphasising that despite this flexibility, most team members have to travel to attend to different tasks, with the exception of activities on Kilou.ma for which a time slot is mentioned.

This information highlights the fact that time flexibility may be conditioned by specific requirements linked to travel and the coordination of activities outside the platform.

The fact that team members have to travel to respond to different tasks highlights the importance of professional commitments and activities requiring physical presence. It may

also indicate that time flexibility is not absolute and may be influenced by specific operational constraints. The need to respect a time slot for activities on Kilou.ma suggests rigour in time management, even within an online platform. Combining temporal flexibility with the need to travel and respect time slots highlights a balanced approach between flexibility in time management and the need for effective coordination.

This hybrid approach may arise from the specific nature of the work activities involved, highlighting the inherent complexity of managing family and work responsibilities within a family business. The statement also stresses that flexibility is granted in terms of time, but does not specifically mention flexibility related to the workplace.

4.2.3. Confidentiality

The interviewees' statements highlight the issue of confidentiality, defined here as the extent to which a family member can separate their professional life from their personal life. The statements indicate that the interviewees expressed a high degree of separation between these two spheres of their existence, highlighting a specific organisational practice to achieve this, namely the holding of daily closing points. The mention of a 'large degree of separation' between personal and professional life suggests a conscious intention to maintain clear boundaries between these two aspects of life. This can be interpreted as a deliberate strategy to preserve privacy and confidentiality in each area, thus avoiding any potential overlap between family and work obligations.

The practice of holding daily closing points underlines an active commitment to managing the separation between personal and professional life. These regular meetings can serve as a formal mechanism to bring closure to the day's work activities, allowing family members to move on to more personal aspects of their lives once these points have been completed.

This demonstrates a willingness to establish clear time boundaries between work and personal life, helping to maintain confidentiality in both areas.

The regularity of these daily closing points can also encourage open and transparent communication within the family. By discussing the day's professional activities, family members can stay informed and involved in professional developments while maintaining a clear separation when these discussions are closed. This can help to strengthen family cohesion by creating a balance between active participation in professional responsibilities and respect for each member's personal life. The practice of confidentiality appears to be embedded in the family's organisational structure and routines, reflecting a systemic approach

to the management of personal and professional life. This indicates a proactive awareness of the potential challenges associated with family and work life within the family business, and a willingness to adopt specific strategies to preserve individual privacy.

4.3. Intrapreneurial climate (Carlock & al..., 2002)

4.3.1. Non-financial rewards

Statements concerning non-financial rewards, such as respect, recognition, and the opportunity to learn and develop, in the professional context of family members, offer an insight into the organisational culture and motivational dynamics within the family business. The interviewees' responses highlight the value placed on these non-financial rewards, particularly through concrete practices within the team. The fact that most of the interviewees confirmed that they are always self-training, particularly in the field of entrepreneurship, highlights an ongoing commitment to professional development. This underlines a proactive attitude towards learning and building skills, which can contribute to a culture of innovation and continuous improvement within the family business.

The weekly sharing session, held every Wednesday to develop and discuss various innovative ideas, represents a practical application of the opportunity to learn and develop. This initiative underlines the importance attached to creativity and innovative thinking within the team. It also creates a space for collaboration and collective thinking, encouraging mutual recognition and respect for the ideas and contributions of every member of the family. Recognition and respect emerge as fundamental elements in the family business dynamic.

The sharing of innovative ideas during the weekly meeting can be interpreted as a form of recognition of the intellectual contributions of each member. It also reinforces mutual respect within the team, as it creates an environment where everyone feels valued for their unique ideas and perspectives.

The emphasis on these non-financial rewards indicates a deep understanding of the importance of intrinsic motivation and well-being at work. Interviewees seem to recognise that non-financial rewards play a crucial role in job satisfaction and in creating a positive and stimulating work environment.

4.3.2. Working time

The interviewees' statements on working time shed light on an interesting perspective on professional commitment within the family business. The general confirmation that working

time is perceived as more intense, but a source of fulfilment, suggests a particular dynamic associated with the creation and evolution of the entrepreneurial idea.

The idea that working time is more intense can be interpreted as an indication of the investment of energy, effort and dedication that family members devote to the family business.

This intensity could stem from the multiplicity of responsibilities assumed within the business, a frequent feature of family businesses where members are often involved in various aspects of the operation. Justifying this intensity by the fact that the idea was created by themselves underlines a strong emotional link with the entrepreneurial project. The feeling of ownership and personal contribution to the evolution of the idea can be a motivating source that transcends the simple measure of working time.

This emotional relationship with the company can contribute to deep job satisfaction and a sense of achievement. The pleasure derived from seeing the idea grow and evolve adds a significant dimension to the perception of working time. This positive experience suggests that the time invested is experienced as an active contribution to the growth of the family business. The satisfaction derived from visualising the development of the idea can reinforce intrinsic motivation, leading to a lasting commitment despite the intensity of the work.

The combination of work intensity with personal fulfilment highlights the complexity of the relationship between work effort and individual satisfaction within the family business. It may also reflect an approach where the quality of the work experience, in terms of personal fulfilment and growth, takes precedence over the sheer quantity of hours spent.

It would be interesting to understand how this perception of working time affects family dynamics and the management of responsibilities within the team.

In addition, exploring how this personal satisfaction contributes to the resilience and sustainability of the family business could provide further insights into the relationship between working time and organisational success. In conclusion, the interviewees' statements highlight a nuanced perspective on working time within the family business. The perceived intensity is counterbalanced by the fulfilment derived from the creation and evolution of the idea, underlining the complexity of motivations and job satisfaction within the family. This unique emotional relationship with the business can play a key role in maintaining the commitment and motivation of family members.

4.3.3. Family time

The interviewees' responses regarding working time highlight an interesting perspective on work commitment within the family business. The statement suggests that, although working time may be more intense, it is also a source of fulfilment, largely because family members see their own idea grow and evolve, thus experiencing personal satisfaction. The fact that interviewees confirmed that working time is more intense underlines the extra dedication and effort invested in the family business.

This intensity may stem from the intrinsic nature of entrepreneurship, where family members are often required to wear several hats and take on a variety of responsibilities. This reality reinforces the idea that working within the family business can be demanding, but it also underlines the passion and commitment to the family project. Organisational boundaries.

4.3.4. Role clarity

The statements concerning role clarity within the family business highlight the importance of the precise definition of the responsibilities of each family member. The statement indicates that the degree of role clarity is explained by the availability and clarity of information, enabling everyone to carry out their tasks in a transparent manner. The fact that information is described as available and clear highlights the particular attention paid to internal communication within the family business. Transparent information about roles and responsibilities helps to create an environment where every member of the family can clearly understand what is expected of them.

This can build trust and minimise ambiguity, encouraging better coordination and collaboration within the team. The association between the availability of clear information and the ability of each member to carry out their role transparently suggests a proactive approach to managing responsibilities. Role clarity is not just about defining tasks, but also about providing relevant information to enable everyone to carry out their responsibilities effectively.

The statement does not specify whether role clarity is the result of formal job descriptions or informal communication within the family. Further exploration of these mechanisms could provide additional insights into how role clarity is established and maintained over time.

The correlation between role clarity and each member's ability to perform their tasks highlights the importance of role clarity to the overall performance of the family business. Well-defined roles can contribute to increased productivity, greater operational efficiency and

a balanced distribution of responsibilities. The crucial aspect of this statement is that, despite the intensity of the work, family members find it fulfilling. This highlights a powerful intrinsic motivation that goes beyond purely financial considerations.

Personal satisfaction seems to stem from the fact that the business idea is the fruit of their own creativity and hard work, creating a strong emotional bond with the project. The specific mention of the pleasure of seeing the idea grow and evolve adds an emotional and dynamic dimension to professional satisfaction. This suggests a deep involvement in the process of developing the family business, where the success of the business is experienced as a personal achievement.

This experience can also be a source of pride and gratification, reinforcing the link between the time invested in work and the feeling of accomplishment. The statement also emphasises the qualitative dimension of working time, which goes beyond the mere number of hours devoted. Fulfilment is linked to the quality of the work experience, where autonomy, creativity and the opportunity to see the fruits of one's labour play an essential role.

4.3.5. Role independence

Interviewees' responses regarding the degree of independence of roles within the family business highlight a flexible and collaborative approach to the allocation of responsibilities. The statement suggests that the degree of independence varies according to the nature of the roles and their importance, and that the family shares its know-how while having the capacity to exchange tasks, when necessary, particularly in times of crisis or in the face of tight deadlines. The observation that the degree of independence depends on roles and their importance underlines a recognition of the diversity of functions within the family business. This adaptive approach suggests that the family is aware that some roles may require more independence due to their strategic or specialist nature, while others may be more collaborative.

The practice of sharing expertise within the family indicates a culture of collaboration and mutual learning.

The transfer of skills between members strengthens organisational resilience by ensuring that several family members are competent in different areas, thereby reducing dependency on specific individuals. This contributes to the sustainability of the family business by creating a diverse skills base. The idea that family members can swap tasks in the event of a crisis or tight deadlines promotes flexibility and solidarity within the team.

This reactive approach allows available resources to be optimised by quickly adapting roles according to the company's immediate needs. It can also strengthen the sense of unity and support within the family, encouraging a collective response to challenges. The absence of a rigid structure of role independence reflects a pragmatic approach that recognises the need to adjust the division of labour as circumstances dictate. This can contribute to a dynamic organisational culture, where agility and collaboration are encouraged to ensure the resilience and success of the family business.

5. Findings

In order to position the case of our company, we referred to Theodore T. Herbert and Deborah Brazeal, who classify organisations into four main categories according to their level of commitment to entrepreneurship: - Intrapreneurial organisations with a high level of commitment;

- Intrapreneurial organisations with a medium level of commitment;

- Occasional intrapreneurial organisations with a low level of commitment;

- Companies with an intrapreneurial challenge without any involvement in entrepreneurial activities. The organisation studied in this research had a high level of commitment to intrapreneurship and seemed to fit best into category 2.

To become an intrapreneurial organisation, the internal environment of an organisation must be changed. Given all the conditions of this organisation, in order to increase their entrepreneurial capacity, they should manage intrapreneurial activities with the help and support of the organisation's management.

Therefore, this organisation should not consider the activities of the suggestion system as the only position for entrepreneurship to flourish; intrapreneurship should encompass all dimensions of the organisation.

Finally, the very first step in achieving an entrepreneurial organisation is to formulate strategies and set objectives based on intrapreneurship. This cannot be done without managers developing an indispensable vision of the different aspects of intrapreneurship.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study highlights the crucial importance of organisational aspects in encouraging intrapreneurship within family businesses in Morocco. The results significantly highlight the decisive role of corporate culture, organisational policies and practices, and

internal structures in stimulating innovation and entrepreneurial initiative within these family-owned entities. The in-depth analysis carried out in our case study clearly demonstrates the positive impact of a corporate culture that encourages creativity and risk-taking. A culture that encourages the free expression of innovative ideas and values individual initiative is essential for creating an environment conducive to the emergence of intrapreneurial projects within family businesses. The findings also highlight the critical importance of organisational policies and practices that actively support intrapreneurial initiatives. Policies that favour the allocation of resources dedicated to innovative projects, as well as practices that encourage collaboration and the recognition of entrepreneurial initiatives, contribute greatly to nurturing a climate conducive to intrapreneurship within family structures.

In addition, flexible and agile organisational structures have been identified as essential levers for facilitating intrapreneurship within family businesses. Organisations that favour cross-functional communication, decentralised decision-making and flexibility in internal processes are better positioned to catalyse and support entrepreneurial initiatives within their teams.

The managerial implications of this study are undeniable for Moroccan family businesses wishing to promote intrapreneurship.

They underline the importance of cultivating a dynamic and innovative corporate culture, while adopting appropriate policies and practices that actively encourage entrepreneurial initiative within the family and its employees. From a scientific point of view, this research contributes to enriching the academic understanding of intrapreneurship in the specific context of family businesses in Morocco. It also raises relevant questions for future studies, particularly on family governance mechanisms and the intergenerational dynamics influencing entrepreneurial innovation within these organisations. Although this study offers substantial insights, it is not without its limitations. The nature of the single case study and the limited sample size call for caution in generalising the results. Further research, with larger samples and a comparative approach, could deepen our understanding of intrapreneurship within Moroccan family businesses.

In conclusion, this study highlights the strategic importance of organisational aspects in promoting intrapreneurship within Moroccan family businesses. The recommendations drawn from this research offer concrete avenues for guiding managerial decisions and fostering an environment conducive to innovation and growth within these family entities, thereby contributing to the economic dynamism and sustainability of family organisations in the country.

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